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PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION'S ASPECTS: A REPRESENTATION OF INCONGRUITY OFFICES FOR INDIVIDUALS WITH HANDICAPS AT THE BIMA RULE, INDONESIA, SAPE SUB-REGION OFFICE

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Abstract: This qualitative study aims to

1) Comprehend the dimensions of public services, specifically the ironic portrayal of facilities and services for people with disabilities;

2) Knowing vital stages to build the limit of public specialist co-ops for people with handicaps in the Sape sub-region office;

3) Be familiar with the handicap-accessible facilities and infrastructure at the Sape District Office.

We conducted a series of in-depth interviews with people with disabilities who receive limited services in Sape District to gather data on the dimensions of this service as well as the limitations of other disability services at the Sape District office. We mention observable facts around the area, as need might arise. Because we selected a qualitative description for the study's data reporting. Our information examination went through a few phases, including the coding system, inside and out understanding, and result recovery by guaranteeing that the discoveries information responded to investigate inquiries with the standards of the discoveries' legitimacy and dependability. According to the findings, adequate service facilities as required by the Undang law have not been provided in Sape Sub-district for a variety of reasons, particularly accessibility issues. As a result, these findings ought to be useful suggestions for future enhancements.

Keywords: Services for the disabled; satire portrait; observations; public services; Sape region

INTRODUCTION

The Sape District office's implementation of public services is unfriendly to people with disabilities. This is an unfortunate and embarrassing portrayal of the law's mandate for public service providers, particularly those providing services to people with disabilities. At the Sape District Office, public services do not provide facilities in the form of space for people with special needs because all of the facilities are for

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regular people. This reality is in opposition to the order of regulation. Facilities and services for people with disabilities ought to be of the highest quality. Real service must be evaluated as a concrete configuration that is inclusive of all segments of society, particularly older people and people with disabilities.

There is no true spirit or essence of service as a quality, productive service cycle that is accessible to people with disabilities because of low service governance, which adds to the long list of blurred portraits of bureaucratic services. So that the government's introduction of regulations that support society's existence as customer service should be an opportunity rather than a challenge for society's interdependence on the government. As required by law, disability-accessible space also becomes a special concern. so that the phenomenology of the lack of facilities and services does not turn into a heartbreaking irony because people are aware that the government is incapable of providing services that are of high quality, accurate, and trustworthy.

The issue of whether service providers are aware of and comprehend the type of quality service has been brought up by this occurrence. Researchers think that providers are aware of this, but they don't have the credibility to fully implement it because they don't know enough about quality service standards. the misconception that people with disabilities are entitled to state services. According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO), people with disabilities make up about 15% of the world's population. In Indonesia alone, 36,150,000 people, or about 15% of the country's 260 million people in 2011, were disabled. The Ministry of Social Affairs' Pusdatin 2018 report shows that 3,842,303 people lived in 33 provinces with severe disabilities in 2018.

The service provider and the service recipient must be connected through service support facilities. Facilities, according to Tjiptono (1995), are physical resources that must be adequate before consumers can receive services. In the meantime, Kotler (1987) says; According to Kotler (2009), facilities consist of all physical equipment provided by the service provider for the convenience of the customer. According to Lupiyoadi & Hamdani (2006), one theorist defines facilities as "the appearance, the ability of the infrastructure, and the condition of the surrounding environment in showing their existence to the external," which includes facilities in the form of tools, objects, equipment, money, and workspace. Other theorists define facilities as "the condition of the surrounding environment in showing their existence to the external."

Regarding accessibility rights for people with disabilities, Law No. 8 of 2016 includes the right: to gain access to public facilities and letter b, specifically to gain adequate accommodation as a form of accessibility for individuals, respectively. The work to level the privileges of people with handicaps is one piece of satisfying common freedoms. The government and local governments are required to plan, organize, and evaluate the implementation, respect, protection, and fulfillment of the rights of persons with disabilities, as stated in paragraph 1 of article 27 (Boland et al., 2009; Scott and Havercamp, 2015). Be that as it may, the presence of disablable isn't practically identical to the privileges they get; getting a

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right, like the right to work in the public sector on one's own and with the same dignity as someone who is not disabled, still results in discrimination.

Less than 30% of people with disabilities receive regular public services. Concerning the following categories of disabled people's rights in light of Article 5 paragraph 1: the need for life; without the stigma of privacy and legal safeguards; education; cooperatives, entrepreneurship, and employment; health; political; religious; sports; tourism and culture; social security; accessibility; public help; shielding against objects; habilitation and recovery; concession; collection of data; maintain one's independence while participating in society; communicating, conveying, and acquiring data; change spot and identity; and unaffected by discrimination, abuse, neglect, and exploitation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This subjective review expected to figure out the elements of public administrations: an ironic depiction of the facility for people with disabilities at the Bima Regency's Sape sub-district office. In February of 2020, the data collection was carried out. We have collected a variety of data to understand the purpose of this study, including interviews with disabled individuals, observations of the location of the Sape sub-district office, and the necessary documentation. After that, we conducted a descriptive analysis of the data, followed by a phenomenological approach, coding, and in-depth interpretation to guarantee that our data findings are valid and reliable in answering the research questions. We followed Miles and Huberman's theory for this reason (1994).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Services for people with disabilities at the Sape sub-district office the observation was that the community distinguishes who requests the service, making it appear promising. However, we observe that providing services to people with disabilities is challenging. We mean difficulties like: deaf, blind, and so on. We only anticipate the intention and purpose of coming to the sub-district office because the communications we convey occasionally do not arrive and are not understood by them. The Sape sub-district government has to work around this issue in order to provide disability services. An excerpt from an interview with Mr. Kamarudin, the head of the Sape Sub-District, includes the following:

In order to ensure that the services we provide to the community are carried out flawlessly, we do so without distinguishing anyone. However, we encounter challenges when it comes to serving individuals with disabilities, and the challenges we mean by this are: deaf-blind. We only anticipate the reason people are coming to this Camat office because sometimes the messages we send them do not arrive or are not understood by them.

In accordance with the meeting with Abdurahman, as the top of the social government assistance segment, he said:

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Due to the diverse physical conditions of the disabled, services at the Sape sub-district office continue to be provided in person and have not taken advantage of e-government, making them conventional. In addition, the regular service continues to face facing. This is because there aren't enough people working at the Sape sub-district office. Forms of service for people with disabilities require us to inquire about the purpose for which they are using verbal and nonverbal communication; however, we must also anticipate the outcomes of the communication.

Disabilities are not supported by inaccessible accessibility, a lack of face-to-face services, or a lack of resources. The following is a portion of an interview that Mr. Amirullah conducted while he was serving as head of government:

For administrations for individuals with handicaps, we generally utilize non-verbal correspondence, albeit fundamentally it is difficult, we are as yet attempting so we can know the reason for coming to the sub-region office. In addition, we offer a "MESRA" service as a means of providing services, one of which involves recording an e-ID card. He was invited to take part in the creation of population records.

Relevantly, it turns out that the Bima District Civil Registration and Population Office has introduced "MESRA" services as a service innovation despite the limited resources at the Sape sub-district office. The following was stated in an interview with Mr. Saleh, a 52-year-old resident of Naru, a village in Sape District:

Because I can't walk normally and have disabilities in both legs, I went to the Sape sub-district office and received unsatisfactory service because I had to crawl on both knees to get to the table or counter. Come to me on the seat, not the reverse way around.

The various physical conditions of people with disabilities greatly influence both the function of a service and the conditions of service, which are conditional. The following are the outcomes of the interview with Mr. Muhtar, a 60-year-old Sape District resident from Bugis Village:

I have handicaps in both of my legs yet I have a stick helped so I can walk effectively, to get administration I need to stroll with a stick despite the fact that I need to gradually. I hope that the officers in charge of services and the government of the Sape subdistrict can assist us in making it simpler for us to access it by learning the language so that it can be processed and we can simply wait until it is finished.

Service guidelines

Cutting down on requirements to make life easier for people with disabilities, establishing specialized communication channels, and so on are all examples of service methods. Regarding Mr. Kamarudin's explanation, which he gave as the head of the Sape Sub-District:

The ongoing help rules are just for the overall population, there are no particular rules for handicaps thinking about this is a snag for us in speeding up administrations and breaking long line chains. To be

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able to provide satisfactory service, we require a novel and efficient approach. Sincerely, we are sorry for people with disabilities who wait in long lines.

Mr. Abdullah, a 50-year-old from Bugis, Sape Sub-district, stated, "I forced it to wait because I had already come to this office and wanted me to go home, but the distance is quite far, about three kilometers from here." We need innovative service methods.

Following are the aftereffects of a meeting with Mr. Amirullah as the Top of the Public authority Segment, in particular:

We only use general service methods to serve the community, which aren't good for people with disabilities because they have to follow normal public service flows. We're sorry that they come from a long way away to use facilities that don't work for them and have to use a service method that doesn't work for them. Currently, we are still considering a disability-friendly service method.

The following are the outcomes of an interview with Mr. Murtada, a 29-year-old resident of Lamere Village:

As a disabled person, I have to use this method of service because the Sape sub-district government does not have a method of service that is meant for us and accommodates us as a way to make it easier for us to get access to adequate services. As a result, we need a method of service that is simple and quick for us to use.

The following are the conclusions drawn from Ruslan's interview as Head of the Physical, Facilities, and Infrastructure Section:

In this regard, we absolutely require a novel service model in order to specifically accommodate people with disabilities. We observe that they must adhere to a service flow that is not appropriate for them, which we do with pity but try to prioritize when they come here.

Placing accountable service

In order to maintain a sense of accountability, officers in the Sape sub-district should assign employees based on their competence. As a result, their systemically inadequate performance is not surprising given the large number of employees lacking competence. S. Sos, as the head of the Sape Sub-District, is, as Mr. Kamarudin explains:

We place representatives as indicated by their capacities with the goal that our representatives can work ideally. In this instance, we are aware that employees lack professional development opportunities. They don't know how services for people with disabilities work because, on average, they haven't been trained on them.

Mr. Abdullah, a 50-year-old resident of Bugis village in the Sape subdistrict of the Bima Regency, stated:

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I believe I must assign employees or service officers based on their skills and knowledge. Thusly it should be suitable in light of the fact that it will be answerable for the command that is done. The position is useless if it is held by an incompetent individual who lacks the necessary skills.

The interview with Mr. Amirullah, S. Sos, who is in charge of the Government Section, is as follows:

We attempt to put workers as per their mastery and capability. We always put credibility first because the responsibility for the position and the employee is one and the same thing. Also, keep in mind that a person's ability will also change depending on the position and the class of employees. Not all employees who have expertise can be put in the right position because the requirements for different positions will ultimately depend on the employee's class.

It will take a long time to issue a license even though the conditions are right; however, an error in issuing a license is a sign that it is incompetent, so to produce a speed of service, experts must be occupied. If an employee is placed in the right position, the results of their performance will be felt because the position they are assigned is following the condition of ability, such as to permit services if done by non-experts.

Although the development is based solely on the grand design and does not take into account people with disabilities, space for those with disabilities has not been provided because the existing facilities are only available to the general public at this time. Other facilities, including information centers, information boards, complaint booths, restrooms, and stairs, are not accommodating to them (people with disabilities). Despite the challenges we face in accommodating the disabled, we only make use of the facilities that are already in use by the community as a whole.

DISCUSSION

We will discuss the significance of the facility findings or public services dimensions in this discussion section. This section also compares the findings of previous studies to a portrait of the handicap facilities at the Sape Sub-District Office. People with disabilities have access to accessibility facilities, and they have rights and benefits from facilities and systems that are unique in nature or entity. The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and their right to have access to what they need, which enables the use of supporting technology following the standards of each region or country, are often the focus of the concept of facilities for people with disabilities or special needs. The findings are consistent with the findings of a 2017 study by Thohari that looked at how important it was for people with disabilities in Malang to have accessible public spaces and facilities for people with disabilities.

The requirements for social disability services were investigated by Hikmawati and Rusmiyati (2011). (2017) Marani; Priscilla (2016a); According to Gumelar and Hanny Hafiar (2018), the Sape District government's limited facility makes it difficult to provide disability services, necessitating strategic measures. For instance, public facilities must be redesigned to better accommodate people with disabilities. Additionally, due to the mandate of the law governing the universal rights of people with disabilities, policymaking requires sensitivity. Even though COVID-19 is here, the Sape sub-district office

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still provides excellent face-to-face conventional services. It has not implemented an electronic government system (E-Gov), which is the cause of this trend. Despite concerns about time inefficiency and queues, the application of face-to-face services is still an option. Face-to-face services have advantages and disadvantages, especially for people with disabilities.

CONCLUSION

The best disability services for people with disabilities necessitate means of communication. To accomplish this, two-way communication, specifically asking people with disabilities for their requirements, is required. The state must prioritize providing high-quality verbal and nonverbal services if our findings are to be considered valid. For instance, open offices, a maintainable framework, further developed help with compassion, dependable help, and sureness. In essence, this empathy for people with disabilities must be incorporated into the preparation of all facilities. When receiving service, an assurance in the form of guarantees is a promise that the government must fulfill as a security guarantee, such as ensuring that the documents are free of errors or administrative loopholes.

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